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Report from non-destructive testing

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Authors:

Name	Institution	Date
Vladimir Slugen	STUBA	10.7.2025
Milan Pavuk	STUBA	11.7.2025
Július Dekan	STU BA	29.7.2025
Jana Simeg Veternikova	STUBA	31.7.2025

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Content

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Investigated Materials and Testing Conditions	4
3. Experimental methods.....	5
3.1 Positron annihilation spectroscopy (PAS).....	5
3.1.1 Principle of the PAS method.....	5
3.1.2 Experimental Setup of PAS	6
3.2 Mössbauer spectroscopy (MS)	6
3.2.1 Principle of the MS method.....	6
3.2.2 Experimental Setup of MS	7
3.3 Atomic force microscopy (AFM).....	7
3.3.1 Principle of the AFM method	7
3.3.2 Experimental Setup of AFM.....	7
4. Assumption of microstructural change due to NPP operation	7
5. Results.....	8
5.1 PAS results	8
5.2 MS results	13
5.3 AFM results	18
6. Summary	23
7. References	24

List of abbreviations

AFM	Atomic Force Microscopy
BCC	Body Cubic Centred (structure)
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
FCC	Face Cubic Centred (structure)
LTO	Long-Term Operation
MS	Mössbauer spectroscopy
NDT	Non-destructive testing
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PAS	Positron Annihilation Spectroscopy

1. Introduction

This Report summarises the results from the non-destructive testing (NDT) focused on the microstructure features of the experimental studied samples, as was planned in the DELISA-LTO experimental matrix described in D4.4: Detailed test matrix for the thermal ageing evaluation experimental program [1]. STUBA performed presented measurements during the project period M24 and M38 according to the timeline plans.

2. Investigated Materials and Testing Conditions

The DELISA-LTO project has compiled a set of structural steels representing both austenitic and low-alloyed materials used in key components of VVER-440 and VVER-1000 reactors. These materials were selected for their relevance to long-term operation (LTO) assessment and suitability for in-depth microstructural analysis using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Mössbauer Spectroscopy (MS), and Positron Annihilation Spectroscopy (PAS). Investigated samples are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Investigated samples by NDT techniques at STUBA.

No.	Sample	Reactor Type	Steel Grade	Operational Status
1	Main circulation piping	VVER-440	08Ch18N12T	initial state (V1 NPP)
2	Pressurizer surge line	VVER-440	08Ch18N10T	initial state (EBO3 NPP)
3a	Main circulation piping	VVER-440	08Ch18N12T	operated at 294 °C for 28 years (V1 NPP)
5	Pressurizer surge line	VVER-1000	08Ch18N10T	operated at 274 °C for 28 years (V1 NPP)
6c	Reactor flange fastening parts - stud	VVER-1000	38KhN3MFA	operated at 305 °C for 30 years (IPP-C)
6d	Reactor flange fastening parts - nut	VVER-1000	38KhN3MFA	operated at 240 °C for 30 years (IPP-C)
7	Steam generator collector with HE tubes	VVER-1000	08Ch18N10T/ 10GN2MFA	operated at 280-315 °C (IPP-C)
8	Main circulation piping	VVER-1000	10GN2MFA +SS cladding	initial state (IPP-C)
9a	Capsules of the thermal specimens	VVER-440	08Ch18N10T	operated at 278 °C for 24 years (Paks NPP)
9b				operated at 278 °C for 32 years (Paks NPP)
10	Main circulation pump - Guide wheel	VVER-440	10H18N9TL	operated for 27 years (EK-CER)

Materials were chosen based on:

- known or estimated operational exposure in nuclear service,
- structural relevance (e.g., piping, welds, internals),
- suitability for comparative characterisation (aged vs. archive),

as reported in Deliverables D2.2 [2] and D2.5 [3] of the DELISA-LTO project.

All studied samples are austenitic stainless steels, except steel 38KhN3MFA and 10GN2MFA. A total of ten samples were investigated for seven different primary loop components by three non-destructive techniques in the as-received conditions, which means that no additional experimental treatment was done at STUBA, except for sample preparation. As the samples were in their initial state or after the operation in NPP, it was possible to observe microstructural changes due to real operation at elevated temperature for a longer time.

3. Experimental methods

Our measurement was focused on the microstructure evaluation by application of the NDT techniques for one or two samples prepared from the as-received material, gradually delivered from VUJE. The obtained samples were mostly in the shape of SPT samples or small prisms. Samples were cut into small circles with a diameter of 8 mm or small squares 8 mm x 8 mm x 0.5 mm, and then ground into a mirror level for PAS. The samples for AFM had to be electropolished and electro-etched to decrease surface roughness and highlight the grains. To prevent contamination of samples for MS transmission measurements with iron atoms, samples in the form of powder were prepared by using a diamond-coated titanium drill.

3.1 Positron annihilation spectroscopy (PAS)

PAS is a sensitive, non-destructive technique for detecting open-volume defects in solids, such as vacancies, dislocations and voids. Within the DELISA-LTO project, PAS is used to monitor microstructural changes due to long-term thermal ageing in construction materials, including both austenitic and low-alloy ferritic steels.

3.1.1 Principle of the PAS method

In PAS, positrons emitted by a β^+ radioactive source, typically ^{22}Na , are implanted into the tested material. After thermalisation, they diffuse through the lattice until they annihilate with an electron, producing two gamma photons (each with energy 511 keV) emitted in opposite directions.

The time between the emission of a prompt 1.274 MeV γ -photon (from ^{22}Na decay) and the detection of the annihilation 511 keV γ -photon is measured. The resulting positron lifetime depends on the local electron density: the lower the density (e.g. near vacancies), the longer the positron lives. Typical positron lifetimes in iron structures are [2, 4]:

~110 ps in defect-free metals (bulk lifetime),

- ~120 -140 ps in bulk together with dislocations,
- ~150–180 ps for dislocations and monovacancies,
- ~190–300 ps for small vacancy clusters (di-vacancies up to 5 vacancies),
- ~300–500 ps for bigger vacancy clusters and nanovoids.

3.1.2 Experimental Setup of PAS

The positron source (^{22}Na encapsulated in Kapton foil) is placed between two identical samples in a sandwich configuration. PAS measurements were performed using digital lifetime spectrometry systems equipped with BaF_2 scintillation detectors, constant fraction discriminators (Ortec 583), and a high-resolution Acqiris DP240 digitiser [5]. For evaluation of results from PAS, the Program LT9 [6] was used, and the standard trapping model was applied. The first lifetime (LT1) can be a combination of positron annihilation in the defect-free structure (bulk) and small defects (dislocations and monovacancies), and the second lifetime (LT2) describes defects. The third lifetime (LT3) is annihilation in air between the sample and the positron source, which was not compensated during the process of reference sample fitting. The intensity I2 is proportional to the amount of the defects described by the LT2 value (the vacancy defects).

3.2 Mössbauer spectroscopy (MS)

MS is a nuclear resonance technique particularly suitable for investigating the structural and magnetic characteristics of iron-containing compounds. It provides unique information on the phase composition, magnetic ordering, and electronic environment of ^{57}Fe atoms. In the DELISA-LTO project, MS is employed to characterise thermally aged low-alloyed and austenitic steels, especially in detecting transformations of Fe-rich phases due to long-term operation.

3.2.1 Principle of the MS method

Mössbauer spectroscopy is based on the recoil-free resonant absorption of γ -radiation (the Mössbauer effect). A radioactive $^{57}\text{Co}(\text{Rh})$ source emits 14.4 keV γ -rays, which are absorbed by ^{57}Fe nuclei in the sample if the nuclear energy levels align. These levels are highly sensitive to the local chemical and magnetic environment, allowing detailed insight into phase transformations, precipitate formation, and segregation phenomena [7].

The main hyperfine parameters extracted from the spectra are:

- Isomer Shift (IS) – related to the s-electron density at the nucleus and oxidation state;
- Quadrupole Splitting (QS) – indicative of electric field gradient and site asymmetry;
- Hyperfine Magnetic Field (B) – reflects magnetic ordering and is characteristic of BCC Fe phases.

Mössbauer spectra of magnetically ordered phases (such as $\alpha\text{-Fe}$) typically display sextets, whereas paramagnetic phases ($\gamma\text{-Fe}$) show singlets or doublets.

3.2.2 Experimental Setup of MS

Measurements are performed in transmission geometry at room temperature using a Wissel constant-acceleration spectrometer. The $^{57}\text{Co}(\text{Rh})$ source is mounted on a drive system to induce Doppler shifts, and the transmitted γ -rays are detected behind the sample using a specialised NaI(Tl) scintillation detector. The sample, typically pulverised investigated material (a few milligrams), is sealed in a thin plastic holder [8]. The MS spectrum evaluation was performed using software CONFIT [9].

3.3 Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

AFM is a non-destructive, high-resolution technique used to characterise the surface morphology and nanoscale features of materials. In the DELISA-LTO project, AFM is employed to investigate surface degradation phenomena due to thermal ageing in structural steels, such as grain boundary oxidation, pit formation, and microcrack initiation.

3.3.1 Principle of the AFM method

AFM operates by scanning a sharp probe mounted on a flexible cantilever across a sample surface. Interatomic forces between the probe tip and the sample deflect the cantilever, and this deflection is measured using a laser beam reflected into a position-sensitive photodetector. A feedback system maintains constant interaction force between the tip and the surface by adjusting the vertical position of the scanner. That enables the generation of a high-resolution, three-dimensional surface topography. AFM can also record phase contrast images to reveal variations in mechanical properties such as stiffness or adhesion at the nanoscale [10].

3.3.2 Experimental Setup of AFM

AFM measurements are performed using a Veeco/Bruker Dimension Edge™ system located at the STUBA Atomic Force Microscopy Laboratory. The system is mounted on a pneumatic anti-vibration table and enclosed in a soundproof cover to ensure high precision [11]. The scanning was performed in contact mode using a silicon nitride probe with a nominal tip radius of 2 nm. Scan sizes of 20x20, 50x50 and 100x100 μm^2 were used, limited by large surface protrusions on the samples.

4. Assumption of microstructural change due to NPP operation

According to the information from literature and EU project research [12-18], which is treated in the Deliverables D4.7 [13] and D6.2 [18], we expect the following effects in the measured samples exposed to NPP conditions:

- Sensitisation through Cr-depletion: M₂₃C₆ carbide precipitation at grain boundaries in austenitic steels and M₃C/M₇C₃ or phosphorus grain boundary segregation in low alloyed steels.

- Formation of secondary α -ferrite or σ -phase in welds or thermally aged zones due to Ni-depletion in austenitic steels.
- Void and dislocation loop formation detectable via PAS, especially in samples 6, 9a and 9b, exposed for 30, 24 and 32 years.
- Surface roughness evolution and intergranular cracking observable via AFM in long-term operated components.
- Tempering of bainite/martensite, leading to softening and microstructural coarsening in samples no.6 and no.7.

5. Results

5.1 PAS results

All PAS results are shown in Fig. 1 as positron lifetime describing defects (LT2) and in Fig. 2 showing intensities of individual lifetimes – for bulk and dislocations (I1) belonging to positron lifetime ≈ 120 -140 ps and for bigger defects (I2) relevant to LT2. The Mean lifetime is shown in Fig. 3.

The detected defects for all samples can be divided into 4 groups:

- dislocation and monovacancies, which were observed in material no.6 (samples no.6c and no.6d). These materials probably do not contain bigger defects as the intensity of dislocations and monovacancies (Fig.2b) is almost on the upper detection limit ($\sim 10^{24}$ defects/m³ [19]),
- divacancies found in the initial state of the main circulation piping,
- three vacancies found for samples no.2, no.7, no.8, no.9 and no.10,
- and smaller vacancy cluster from 4 to 6 vacancies in sample no.3a, no.5 and no.8.

Figure 1. PAS results: Positron Lifetimes for defects (LT2).

The results indicated that all samples contain dislocations, which were observed in the first lifetime component (LT1) in combination with the bulk value, and for samples no. 6c and 6d, also by the value of LT2. For other samples, also bigger defect complexes

of more vacancies were detected. The Mean Lifetime for the samples showed a difference between individual states of thermal ageing described below.

Figure 2. PAS results: a) Positron Intensities for bulk and small defects (I1), b) Positron Intensities for bigger defects (I2).

Figure 3. PAS results: Mean Lifetime (uncertainty ± 2 ps) describing the total open volume in samples.

The results for 08ChN0T steels: 08Ch18N10T and 08Ch18N12T are specially displayed in Fig.4 - lifetime values (LT2) and Fig.5 – intensities (I2) for better comparison of the thermal ageing.

Figure 4. PAS results: Positron Lifetimes for defects in steel 08Ch18N10T.

Figure 5. PAS results: Positron Intensities for defects in steel 08Ch18N10T.

The comparison of the main circulation piping (12T) and surge line (10T) in Fig.4 and Fig.5 shows the initial state (sample no.1 and no.2) as well as their state after the thermal ageing in NPP for 28 years (no.3a and no.5). PAS results demonstrated that the surge line contains bigger defects in the initial state (3-vacancies) than the main circulation piping (di-vacancies). Still, after the NPP operation, the defect size is similar (probably 4 vacancies in predominance) independently of the operating temperature. The difference between the sizes of these defects is very small. Although results indicated the existence of one size of defects, the reality shows that this size is predominant and there exist more defect sizes in the structure. During the NPP operation, smaller defects probably joined into bigger ones, but with the final smaller

concentration, as the change of intensities (I₂) showed decrease from 20 to 40 % (see Fig.5). The decrease of calculated Mean Lifetime values found after the NPP operation (see Fig.3) indicates reducing of the total open volume but with presence of bigger defects as previous.

Samples no.7, no.9a, and no.9b indicated only defects of three vacancies with intensities around 20 % as was also found in other operated samples. Due to the absence of initial samples for these NPP components, we can compare them only with the initial state of the surge line (the same material and chemical composition). Herewith, the same effect as for the surge line and main circulation piping material was found – accumulation of small defects with a total smaller concentration of open volume defects.

PAS results for samples no.9a and no.9b showed almost the same-sized defects after 24 and 32 years of operation with a smaller value of the Mean Lifetime value (Fig.3) and defect intensities in comparison to the initial sample (no.2), which were reduced due to NPP operation, as for sample no.2 and no.7. However, after longer thermal ageing – for comparison of sample no.9a and no.9b, a slight decrease in defect size and increase in defect concentration was seen (2.5%).

During NPP operation at elevated temperature up to 300 °C, the higher kinetic energy of atoms in steels can be visible, which should recombine open volume defects. However, this temperature is too low for evident structure regeneration. However, bigger defects were formed there probably as a result of more compacted spacing in the FCC structure and due to a mechanism of energy lowering. This vacancy cluster tends to form stable vacancy loops or stacking fault tetrahedra, as was described in [20].

The PAS results for low alloyed steel (no.6) and cast austenitic steel (no.10), as well as a combination of austenitic and low alloy steels (no.7 and no.8), are shown in Fig.6 – Lifetime 2 and Fig. 7 – Intensity 2. The Mean Lifetime for no.10 and no.7 (Fig.3) is similar to the previously mentioned NPP operated samples no.3a and no.5. We have only one state for samples no.10 and no.7 – after the NPP operation, thus, the thermal ageing effect cannot be shown and compared.

The Mean Lifetime for no.6c and no.6d (both from steel 38KhN3MFA) can be different due to their origin from different components: sample no.6c is from the stud, and no.6d from the nut, which have different thermomechanical loads. Sample no.6c was operated at a higher temperature, 305 °C, with tensile stress and no.6d at a temperature of 240°C with compressive stress. Sample no.6c indicated smaller defects than 6d, although both defects are dislocations in predominance, but in 6d, there are also probably more monovacancies, as the LT2 value is slightly higher. Sample no.6d has lower intensity (proportional to defect concentration) at about 30%.

Sample no.8 shows the biggest defects from the measuring set of experimental samples. Their size is probably 4 or 6 vacancies, small vacancy clusters. The intensity of positron annihilation in these defects is quite small, only 8%, which means a very low concentration of this defect. As we do not have an initial material, we cannot compare whether this is due to thermal ageing or not. Still, due to the effect of defect

joining during NPP operation at elevated temperatures, formation of small voids and microcracks can be assumed in this component, which could lead to the formation of microcracks in this steel/sample.

Figure 6. PAS results – positron lifetime for other steels.

Figure 7. PAS results – positron intensities for other steels.

5.2.1 Conclusion of PAS results

Austenitic steels (e.g., 08Ch18N12T, 08Ch18N10T) showed low positron lifetimes, indicating compact microstructure and low concentration of open-volume defects even after long-term operation. The defects were slightly bigger after the NPP operation, but their concentration slightly decreased.

In low-alloy ferritic-bainitic steels (e.g., 10GN2MFA), PAS results also indicated a compact structure, with no significant signs of thermal degradation or void formation, consistent with their known thermal stability. No significant evidence of microcracks or large voids was detected in any material type.

Overall, PAS results confirm that austenitic and ferritic reactor steels retain a compact structure. Still, austenitic steels may exhibit early signs of microstructural degradation under prolonged thermal exposure, as the defect joining can be typical for this material.

5.2 MS results

All MS measurements were calibrated using standardised 25 μm $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ foil (Goodfellow) and therefore all evaluated isomer shifts are relative to $\alpha\text{-Fe}$. The data contain values of the hyperfine magnetic field (B), which reflects the internal magnetic environment of ^{57}Fe atoms. Pure ferrite typically shows $B_{hf} \approx 33.0$ T, while Cr-alloyed ferritic steels exhibit lower values, around 25–30 T [21]. Our measurements show mostly a B_{hf} value around 25T, indicating a Cr-rich ferritic phase, consistent with thermally aged structural steel. Values around 30 indicate a ferritic phase with moderate alloying, typically due to the presence of elements like chromium or nickel, and B_{hf} around 33 T can indicate pure or nearly pure $\alpha\text{-ferrite}$, suggesting a well-ordered, magnetically saturated ferritic phase without significant alloying effects [22].

Fitting software CONFIT deconvolutes the measured spectra [9] using the following model for all samples:

1.1.1 Model

- (i) **$\alpha\text{-Fe}$** : magnetically ordered iron nuclei in BCC structure with MS spectral parameters remarkably close to an ideal $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ metallic iron ($IS = 0$ mm/s; $QS = 0$ mm/s; $B_{hf} = 33.3$ T). Typically, magnetically ordered compounds are represented in the form of a six-line spectral component, so-called sextet. This **$\alpha\text{-Fe}$** phase is present in samples 6, 7 and 8, and in figures and tables is presented in **dark blue colour**.
- (ii) **Ferritic phase**: magnetically ordered iron nuclei in BCC structure influenced by substitutional impurity atoms, predominantly chromium. These substituent atoms are predominantly influencing the B_{hf} value, reducing the internal field from ideal 33.3 T to 25-30 T, with much broader spectral lines, depending on the concentration of substituents in the nearest neighbourhood of the investigated iron nuclei. Typically, magnetically ordered compounds are represented in the form of a six-line spectral component, so-called sextet. This **ferritic phase** is present in all samples, except sample 3a. Figures and tables are presented in **light blue colour**.
- (iii) **Austenitic phase**: non-magnetic iron nuclei in FCC structure with MS parameters remarkably close to ideal austenite ($IS = 0.11$ mm/s; with no quadrupole or magnetic splitting of energy lines). A single line component represents austenite, also known as a singlet. This non-magnetic **austenitic phase** is present in all samples. The figures and tables are presented in **yellow colour**.

- (iv) **Iron oxides:** magnetically ordered iron nuclei with MS spectral parameters close to Fe_3O_4 . Typically, magnetically ordered compounds are represented in the form of a six-line spectral component, so-called sextet. This phase is present only in sample 7-bulk, and in the figure and table is presented in **red colour**.

In Fig.8, the samples of the main circulation piping are evaluated by MS in the initial state (no.1) and the state after the NPP operation (no.3a). Both samples show almost clear austenitic structure. Sample no.1 contains austenite with 76% and an onset of magnetically ordered state, most probably residual BCC iron. The sample no.3a after the NPP operation shows only clear austenite with a 100% ratio.

Figure 8. MS results for sample no.1 and no.3a.

For samples no. 2 and no.5 from the pressurised surge line, both samples show a similar mixture of iron ferrite (with chromium substituents) and austenite, with the austenite content between 32 and 37%. Sample no.5 has slightly more ferrite and slightly lower B_{hf} value, which may indicate microstructural changes due to NPP operation and probably due to more chromium segregation in the matrix. That is what was initially assumed, but it can also be a little bit different material, as sample no.2 was delivered from V2 NPP (the initial state), not directly from V1, as was sample no.5. The increase of the BCC structure (saturated probably by Cr atoms) was 5% for 28 years.

Figure 9. MS results for sample no.2 and no.5.

Samples from material 9, thermal capsules, are investigated after 24 and 32 years under the NPP operation. Both samples contain austenitic structure between 32 and 36 %, similar to samples no.2 and no.5. Sample 9b (after 32 years of operation) shows higher ferritic content and slightly lower magnetic field (B), compared to 9a (24 years). That indicates progressive FCC-to-BCC transformation, likely caused by long-term thermal ageing and Cr/Ni segregation. The increase in BCC structure is around 4% over 8 years. The lower magnetic field in 9b also suggests increased lattice distortion or chemical heterogeneity in the ferritic phase.

Figure 10. MS results for sample no.9a and no.9b.

Sample no.6 shows a predominantly ferritic microstructure, with 76% of the iron atoms in a nearly pure BCC ferrite phase, characterised by a high hyperfine magnetic field, $B_{hf} \approx 33$ T. The predominant structure is ferritic-bainitic structure, also according to the chemical composition. The presence of an additional magnetically ordered component can be assigned to the ferritic structure with substituents in the nearest neighbourhood. A minor paramagnetic component can be assigned to the retained austenitic fraction, or it can be a signal from iron nuclei trapped in the environment, which suppresses

magnetic interaction (many chromium atoms in the nearest neighbourhood, for instance).

Sample no. 6	A_{rel} [%]	IS [mm/s]	QS [mm/s]	$\langle B_{hf} \rangle$ [T]
α -Fe	76	-0.01	0	33.4
ferritic phase	22	-0.01	0	30.7
austenitic phase	2	-0.01	-	-

Figure 11. MS results for sample no.6.

The sample no.7 (bulk) shows a dominant ferritic phase. The 66% almost pure ferrite with a high $B_{hf} = 33.4$ T represents well-ordered BCC Fe, similar to α -Fe. The 28% component with a B_{hf} value of 30.7 T indicates substituent-modified ferrite, likely containing Cr, Mo, or Ni. A small amount of iron oxides (4%) suggests slight surface oxidation or early corrosion.

The spectrum of the sample no.7 (SS), which should be austenitic steel, reflects a typical distorted ferritic phase (88%) with $B_{hf} = 25.3$ T, which is significantly lower than pure ferrite, indicating the presence of alloying elements (mainly Cr and Ni) that reduce magnetic ordering. The remaining 12% is austenitic (FCC), observed as a paramagnetic singlet with $IS = -0.12$ mm/s, typical for stainless steel. This composition matches a welded or multiphase stainless-steel cladding, likely degraded or transformed over time by thermal stress. That could also be due to sample preparation, as the bulk matrix could contaminate the experimental powder determined for the measurement. Alternatively, a longer time connection of two different materials could allow for chemical element transformation.

Sample no. 7 "bulk"	A_{rel} [%]	IS [mm/s]	QS [mm/s]	$\langle B_{hf} \rangle$ [T]
α -Fe	66	-0.01	0	33.4
ferritic phase	28	-0.01	0	30.7
austenitic phase	2	-0.01	-	-
Fe oxides	4	0.26	0	47.9

Sample no. 7 "pipe"	A_{rel} [%]	IS [mm/s]	QS [mm/s]	$\langle B_{hf} \rangle$ [T]
ferritic phase (bcc)	88	-0.04	0.01	25.3
austenitic phase	12	-0.12	-	-

Figure 12. MS results for sample no.7 – low alloyed steel (bulk) and austenitic steel (SS).

The sample no.8 consists of a strongly alloyed multiphase structure; the samples are from 2 materials – austenitic cladding welded on the low-alloyed steel matrix. The dominant component (66%) is a ferritic phase modified by substituents, such as Cr, Mo, or Ni, which reduces the hyperfine magnetic field to a B_{hf} value of 25.8 T. That is typical for thermally aged or Cr-rich ferrite, where magnetic order is weakened by chemical inhomogeneity or segregation. A smaller portion (9%) shows pure ferrite with a B_{hf} value of 33.2 T, corresponding to a magnetically well-ordered, low-alloyed BCC iron structure. The remaining 25% is austenitic (FCC), visible as a paramagnetic singlet typical of stainless-steel regions. The results confirm that sample no.8 originates from a transition zone, possibly at the interface of austenitic stainless steel and ferritic low-alloy steel, where thermal exposure and alloy intermixing have led to partial transformation and redistribution of alloying elements.

Sample no. 8	A_{rel} [%]	IS [mm/s]	QS [mm/s]	$\langle B_{hf} \rangle$ [T]
α -Fe	9	-0.02	0	33.2
ferritic phase	66	-0.04	0	25.8
austenitic phase	25	-0.12	-	-

Figure 13. MS results for sample no.8.

A sample from material 10, Main circulation pump - guide wheel, is investigated after 27 years of operation at the NPP. The sample contains 21% of austenitic structure, the rest is formed by BCC ferrite with substituents.

Sample no. 10	A_{rel} [%]	IS [mm/s]	QS [mm/s]	$\langle B_{hf} \rangle$ [T]
ferritic phase	79	-0.04	0.02	24.5
austenitic phase	21	-0.12	-	-

Figure 14. MS results for sample no.10.

5.2.1 Conclusion of MS results

From the MS results, it is evident that austenitic steel 08Ch18N12T (sample no.3a) showed 100% FCC structure with no ferritic structure, confirming excellent phase stability after 28 years at 297 °C. It is due to higher nickel contents than in 08Ch18N10T, which stabilises the austenitic (FCC) structure. However, the initial state contains a small BCC phase, probably formed due to the manufacturing process and steel inhomogeneity, as the effect of time degradation without stress is not expected.

In contrast, 08Ch18N10T (sample no.5) steel showed partial transformation with ~18% ferritic phase and B_{hf} value around 25 T, indicating localised transformation and Cr/Ni redistribution. For samples no.9a and no.9b, MS spectra were remarkably similar to sample no. 5, showing also higher ferritic content. Longer aged sample 9b showed advanced ferrite formation (~68%) and intergranular damage, confirming long-term thermal degradation.

Ferritic-bainitic 10GN2MFA-type steels (samples no.6 and no.7-bulk) remained structurally stable, showing dominant ferrite with a B_{hf} value around 33.4 T. Cladding and transition zones (Samples no.7-SS and no.8) revealed mixed structures with Cr-rich ferrite and austenite. Only one sample (no. 7-bulk) featured traces of iron oxides (to the presence of which the MS method is sensitive).

5.3 AFM results

The results of the AFM measurements are shown in Figures 15 to 21. Below each figure, a table presents the height difference between adjacent surface crystals and the RMS roughness. The AFM topography of sample no.1 in the initial state of 08Ch18N12T and sample no.3a after 28 years of NPP operation at ~297 °C, as shown in Fig.15, revealed similar surface morphology with well-defined austenitic grain boundaries. The RMS roughness remained comparable (~102 nm for no.1 vs. 66–122 nm for no.3a), with no signs of surface degradation such as pits or cracks. However, sample no.3a exhibited a slightly increased number of dark spots (pits) after etching along the grain boundaries, possibly indicating the onset of phase separation or precipitate formation, such as chromium-rich carbides or intermetallics. These features suggest early-stage microstructural changes due to long-term thermal exposure, although no severe surface damage was detected.

Figure 15. AFM results for samples no.1 and no.3a, scan size 100x100 μm².

In Fig. 16, there are images of AFM morphology for samples no. 2 in the initial state and no. 5 after the NPP operation of steel 08Ch18N10T. In sample no.2, the surface showed a uniform topography with clearly defined austenitic grains and smooth grain boundaries.

In sample no. 2, pits (black circles) are visible along the grain boundaries, while sample no. 5 shows different colouring of whole grains. The difference between sample no. 5 and no.2 is that sample no. 5 has higher height differences between neighbouring crystals (192 nm versus 162 nm). The higher roughness in sample no. 2 (110 nm) is caused by those pits at the grain boundaries.

In addition to the images shown in Fig.16, an AFM scan from a different surface region is also available for each sample. In both cases, the surface morphology was consistent with that observed in Fig. 16. Therefore, these images in Fig. 16 can be considered representative of the surface of samples no. 2 and no. 5. The average depth of the pits located along the grain boundaries was 795±213 nm (mean ± standard deviation).

Figure 16. AFM results for samples no.2 and no.5, scan size 100x100 μm².

AFM scans of sample no.9a (capsule aged 24 years) displayed a relatively compact surface structure with mild grain boundary contrast and bigger roughness variation than for no.9b. Only limited surface features were observed, indicating early-stage microstructural changes in sample no.9a. For sample no.9b (capsule aged 32 years), the AFM image showed clearly visible grain boundaries, banded structures, and more pronounced localised features, including pits. The topography was more heterogeneous, suggesting progressive intergranular degradation. The surface in no.9b appears more textured and fragmented, implying that thermal ageing over 32 years has accelerated segregation, phase transformation, or void formation along grain boundaries.

Figure 17. AFM results for samples no.9a and no.9b, scan size 50x50 μm² (9a, probably over-etched) and 100x100 μm² (9b).

AFM images of samples: no. 6c, 7, and 8 do not clearly reveal surface features, likely due to slight over-etching during sample preparation. Based on these images, no firm conclusions can be drawn, and the measurements should be repeated on samples prepared with improved surface treatment in future experiments. Problems with the purity of solutions were addressed during electrolytic polishing and etching. However, the resulting surface roughness was still too high for reliable AFM measurements. Therefore, the plasma electro-etching was applied for some samples, although this method proved to be nonoptimal.

Sample no.6c, a low-alloy ferritic steel (10GN2MFA), exhibits a fine-grained ferritic-bainitic microstructure with sharp grain boundaries and relatively uniform surface relief. No signs of localised corrosion, pitting, or intergranular degradation were observed. The surface appears homogeneous, without microcracks or damage patterns.

Sample no.7 exhibited a fine-grained austenitic structure, typical for surface cladding. The topography showed uniform grain shapes with fine relief and no visible signs of damage. No pits, cracks, or localised degradation were observed.

Sample no.8, taken from a region near a weld (on the ferritic steel side), showed a more irregular and rougher surface, with visible surface depressions and non-uniform topography, which can be due to problems with sample preparation or indication of local early corrosion effects.

In summary, samples no.6 and no.7 appear structurally stable, while sample no.8 shows early signs of degradation, likely influenced by thermal gradients or residual stresses near the weld interface.

Sample	no.6c
Average height difference between crystalline grains [nm]	-
RMS Surface Roughness [nm]	155

Figure 18. AFM results for sample no.6c (over-etched), scan size 20x20 μm².

Sample	no.7 (SS)
Average height difference between crystalline grains [nm]	-
RMS Surface Roughness [nm]	257

Figure 19. AFM results for sample no.7 (over-etched), scan size 50x50 μm².

Sample	no.8 (SS)
Average height difference between crystalline grains [nm]	-
RMS Surface Roughness [nm]	211

Figure 20. AFM results for sample no.8 (over-etched), scan size 20x20 μm².

The sample no.10 corresponds to an austenitic stainless steel (10H18N9TL), taken from the guide wheel of the main circulation pump after long-term NPP operation. Its surface revealed a dendritic austenitic structure with no clearly defined grain boundaries. No visible signs of localised degradation, such as pits, intergranular cracks, or precipitate clusters, were observed in the scanned area. The overall surface morphology was compact and continuous, suggesting that the material retained its structural integrity despite long-term thermal exposure and mechanical loading.

Sample	no.10
Average height difference between crystalline grains [nm]	1180
RMS Surface Roughness [nm]	325

Figure 21. AFM results for sample no.10, scan size 100x100 μm².

5.3.1 Conclusion of AFM results

AFM measurements confirmed that austenitic stainless steels largely retained stable surface morphology under thermal ageing conditions, with clear grain boundaries and limited signs of surface degradation. However, in aged materials, local contrast variations and depressions were occasionally observed near grain boundaries, suggesting early stages of segregation or precipitation.

Ferritic and ferritic-bainitic steels exhibited more textured topography, particularly after long-term exposure, where intergranular features and band-like structures became visible. These surface patterns point to progressive microstructural transformation under thermal stress.

6. Summary

The combination of PAS, MS and AFM revealed a consistent picture of the microstructural evolution in steels exposed to long-term NPP operation and thermal ageing.

In austenitic steels, all three methods confirmed the general stability of the matrix structure. MS results showed BCC phase also in the samples before the NPP operation (probably Cr precipitates), which still slightly form by FCC-BCC transformation during the thermal ageing. PAS data indicated middle concentrations of vacancy-type defects and no significant increase in open-volume defects after the NPP operation, although defects were observed to join together. AFM imaging supported these findings, with most surfaces remaining smooth and continuous, though minor contrast variations

near grain boundaries suggested early-stage segregation or precipitation in aged materials.

In low-alloyed ferritic steels, progressive changes were more apparent. MS revealed stable ferritic phases but with features indicating phase evolution and magnetic intensity changes in long-exposed samples. PAS detected mostly dislocations with higher concentration in these samples. AFM scans showed increasingly heterogeneous surface patterns, including banded structures and intergranular features, consistent with thermal degradation mechanisms.

In conclusion, long-term thermal exposure and NPP operation induce gradual microstructural evolution, most visibly in ferritic steels and interface regions. Austenitic steels demonstrated superior resistance (mostly steel with higher Ni content - 08Ch18N12T) with only limited changes detectable at micro- and nanoscales. This multi-technique approach confirms that ageing effects are material-dependent and accumulate with operational time.

7. References

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